

PRODUCTION OF AN ADSORBENT FROM DRIED AND SHREDDED HOUSEHOLD FOOD WASTE

K. PAPADOPOULOU^{1*}, H. PAVLOPOULOS¹, P. GEORGIU¹, A. PEPPAS², G. M. LYTRAS¹, L. ZOUMPOULAKIS¹, G. LYBERATOS^{1,3}

¹ School of Chemical Engineering, National technical University of Athens, Iroon Polytechniou 9, Zografou, 15780, Athens, Greece

² School of Mining and Metallurgical Engineering of the National Technical University of Athens, Iroon Polytechniou 9, Zografou 157 80, Athens, Greece

³ Institute of Chemical Engineering Sciences (ICE-HT), Stadiou Str., Platani, 26504, Patras, Greece

**corresponding author: Konstantina Papadopoulou*

e-mail: kpapado@chemeng.ntua.gr, tel. +302107723115

ABSTRACT

The scope of the current research work was to produce and evaluate an adsorbent generated by pyrolysis/activation of a biomass product, FORBI (Food Residue Biomass), which is produced by drying and shredding source-collected Household Food Waste.

A two-step chemical activation process was used. Pyrolysis conditions (temperature, duration) and activation parameters (chemical agents, impregnation ratio, soak time) affect the properties of the resultant adsorbent significantly. The adsorbent was prepared by chemical activation with KOH. Pyrolysis and activation were conducted at a temperature of 800°C. The sample was impregnated with the chemical agents and then activated at 800°C under constant N₂ flow. The impregnation ratio of carbon / KOH was 1:4. Pyrolysis was carried out in a metallic-tube pyrolytic furnace. FORBI was placed into a metallic carrier located close to the nitrogen inlet. The heating profile in the metallic tube is monitored by a NiCr/Ni thermocouple.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was used in order to assess the thermal stability of biomass (measuring weight loss as a function of temperature or time in a controlled atmosphere). TGA was carried out in a thermal analyzer under dynamic nitrogen (N₂) atmosphere as purge gas, with a flow rate of 10 - 20 cm³/min. The sample (~60 mg) was placed in a cylindrical crucible made of quartz and then heated with a constant heating rate of 10 °C/min from ambient temperature to 1000°C. The information on dynamic residual weight and derivative thermogravimetry (DTG) with temperature was analyzed to determine the decomposition rate and thermal stability.

The obtained adsorbent was characterized by measuring its porosity, pore size distribution and BET surface area. The surface chemical characteristics were determined by FT-IR. The microstructure of the produced activated carbon/adsorbent was examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

In the sequel, the potential of using the generated adsorbent for hexavalent chromium as well as COD removal was examined. Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms were determined.

Keywords: Household Food Waste, adsorbent, FORBI, hexavalent chromium, COD.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to rapid urbanization, industrialization and population increase, the amount of municipal solid waste (MSW) generated is expected to reach 9.5 billion tons by 2050 [1]. In Europe, 88 million tons of food are wasted annually with an overall cost estimated at 143 billion euros [2]. According to Directive 98/2008, biowaste is a biodegradable subset of waste and includes a wide variety of materials, e.g. biodegradable garden, park waste, household food waste and catering waste [3].

Worldwide, the production of fermentable household waste is expected to increase by 44% from 2005 to 2025, especially in developing countries. In Europe, the amount of fermentable household waste is expected to increase from 89 million tons in 2006 to 126 million tons in 2020 [4; 5; 6]. 40% of solid urban waste consists of non-recyclable, compostable household waste (fruit residues, vegetables, cooked food residues, etc.).

The organic fermentable fraction of domestic waste is a heterogeneous substrate, based on the composition and source. The content of household waste can be very different and unpredictable in several countries [7]. Typically, the main fraction of household waste consists of fermentable foods such as rice, meat, fruit, vegetables and cellulose paper, which are biodegradable organic materials rich in carbohydrates, proteins and lipids [8]. The composition of the polymers of carbohydrates (starch, cellulose and hemicellulose), proteins, lipids, fibers and inorganic materials makes compostable household waste a promising raw material (biomass) [9]. The European Commission adopted a legislative proposal in 2014, to review waste related targets in the EU Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC. A very significant development in this area took place recently: the European Parliament adopted the waste legislative proposals on March 17th 2017. With regard to Biowaste, the adopted text includes the following:

- 70% target for recycling of municipal waste with a 5% of that waste to be prepared for reuse by 2030
- Obligatory separate collection for the main waste streams, including biowaste
- Separate collection at the source of biowaste and introduction of European waste codes for municipal biowaste that has been separately collected at the source

EU's food waste reduction target was set at 30% by 2025 and at 50% by 2030 compared to the 2014 baseline [10]. The EU has set an important policy on biowaste management, aiming mostly at prevention of such waste, along with the introduction of municipal management programs of source separated biowaste. These programs greatly depend on the ability of local authorities to effectively organize integrated Biowaste management systems for the prevention and separate collection of biowaste.

Within a Horizon 2020 project called Waste4Think in the Municipality of Halandri, Greece, Household Food Waste (HFW) is collected from 240 households, twice a week. Participants have been provided with 30L portable household bins and biodegradable bags made of starch, while the filled bags are deposited in locked 120 liter bins, proximally located. Residents handle in this manner only kitchen food waste such as cooked food waste, fruit, vegetable, used tissue paper (cellulose), except of bones and fluids. The 120 L bins are collected every 3-4 days by a truck, which will in the future be fueled by biogas produced from FORBI, in a circular economy approach. The collected material is then transferred for drying and shredding in a specially designed area 24m² (Fig.2). The material is heat-treated (92-98°C) and shredded in a GAIA GC-300 dryer/shredder, in order to generate a biomass product, FORBI (Food Residue Biomass product). The treatment takes 9 hours at 92-98°C and 2 hours of cooling with a maximum power usage of 23.8 kW. The exact processing times and energy use vary somewhat, depending mainly on the original waste moisture content. The drying system reduces the weight of the fermentable waste by a percentage reaching up to 75%. The moisture content in the household fermentable waste is high (60-80%). The drying benefits are the reduction of the final volume and weight, the removal of odors and a longer shelf life and product homogeneity [11].

The generated FORBI has been studied as an alternative feedstock for several innovative eco-solutions (i.e. production of gaseous biofuels, biomethane and biohydrogen [12], electricity production by using Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) [13], alternative fuel for cement industry [14], pellet production [15] and bioethanol production [16]. The scope of the current research work was to produce and evaluate an adsorbent generated from FORBI.

Carbon-based adsorbents, such as biochars and activated carbons, can be used in environmental applications to remove pollutants from wastewater or filter drinking water, thanks to their high specific surface area and porosity. However, the fact that they are relatively expensive materials limits their wide application. For this reason sustainable alternative sources of carbonaceous materials have been tested as possible precursors. Food processing wastes are a good source of such carbonaceous precursors and previous research has shown that it is possible to obtain effective adsorbents from raw materials such as walnut shells and jujube seeds [17], bagasse and rice husks [18], coffee grounds [19], rice straw [20], acorns and olive seeds [21].

Fermentable food waste in Greece is a large fraction of the municipal wastes that ends up in landfills. Utilizing this fraction can prove an inexpensive source of a biomass material, reducing simultaneously the total waste volume in landfills.

The scope of the current work is to produce and evaluate an adsorbent utilizing a biomass product derived from the Fermentable Household Waste (HFW) fraction through drying and shredding. Thermogravimetric analysis was used to get an insight on the thermal behavior of this biomass product. A two-stage chemical activation process with KOH is deployed to generate the adsorbent. Physical and chemical characteristics of the product are determined in addition to adsorption experiments in aqueous solutions of Cr(VI) and COD.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of FORBI

TGA was used in order to observe the thermal stability of biomass (FORBI) by measuring weight loss as a function of temperature or time under a controlled atmosphere. FORBI was examined by TGA in order to observe its thermal decomposition behavior prior to the carbonization–activation experiments. TGA was carried out in a thermal analyzer using a dynamic nitrogen (N_2) atmosphere as purge gas, with a flow rate of 10 - 20 cm^3/min . The sample (~60 mg) was placed into a cylindrical crucible made of quartz and then heated at a constant heating rate of 10 $^{\circ}C/min$ from ambient temperature to 1000 $^{\circ}C$.

2.2 Double stage chemical activation

A sample of 110-140g FORBI is dried overnight at 120 $^{\circ}C$ before the pyrolysis takes place in the tube furnace (Fig.1) to prevent excessive fume generation at the early pyrolysis stage. The sample is inserted in the specified thermal zones and heated to 800 $^{\circ}C$ at a rate of 10 $^{\circ}C/min$ under constant N_2 flow. The sample is pyrolyzed at the desired temperature for 1 hour. After the treatment takes place, the sample is pulled out of the high-temperature thermal zones and is allowed to cool overnight before the furnace is opened to extract it.

Figure 1. : A. FORBI biomass, B. Pyrolysis-Activation tube furnace, C. Final product (adsorbent)

The carbonized sample is impregnated in a 10% w/w solution of KOH in a 1:4 carbon to agent ratio for 1 hour at 50°C under stirring conditions. The impregnated sample is filtered and dried overnight at 105°C. Subsequently, the impregnated sample is put on the tube furnace and activated at 800 °C for 1 hour following the procedure used for pyrolysis. Before characterization, the adsorbent was rinsed in 0,1M HCl solution and washed with hot (80-85°C) deionized water until neutralization. The process was repeated 3 times.

2.3 Production of biosorbent from FORBI

2.3.1 Factors affecting biosorption

Biosorption is mainly affected by initial metal ion or/and organic concentration, temperature, pH and biomass (FORBI) concentration.

- Higher initial metal ion or/and organic concentration results in a higher solute uptake. It is necessary to identify the maximum saturation potential of a biosorbent.
- Temperature does not influence the efficiency of biosorption in the range of 20-35°C. Higher temperature enhances sorption due to the increased surface activity and kinetic energy of the solute. Due to the exothermic nature of some adsorption processes, an increase in temperature has found to reduce the biosorption capacity of the biomass such as food waste.
- The pH is observed to be very important due to its ability to affect the solution chemistry of the metals, the activity of functional groups in the biomass and the competition of metallic ions. The pH strongly influences the speciation and biosorption availability of the metal ions. At higher solution pH, the solubility of metal complexes decreases sufficiently, allowing precipitation, which may complicate the sorption process. The activity of binding sites can also be altered by adjustment of the pH.

2.4 Characterization of the adsorbent produced by FORBI

The adsorbent's specific surface area was determined from nitrogen adsorption data obtained from a gas sorption analyzer, NOVA 1200, Quantachrome using BET (Brunauer, Emmet και Teller) method. The samples were degassed under vacuum at 300 °C for 3 h, prior to measurement.

Determination of the chemical compounds of the samples was performed on a Fourier transform spectrophotometer, FT-IR Spectrum 100, by Perkin Elmer. To obtain the FT-IR spectra, tablets were prepared by mixing a small amount of each sample with potassium bromide (KBr) and placing the mixture in a suitable press.

Optical information about the structure of the adsorbent was obtained through SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy) images, using a JEOL, 6360LV scanning microscope.

2.5 Adsorption of Cr(VI) and COD

The performance of the adsorbent was evaluated by adsorption isotherm experiments. Batch experiments were conducted for the adsorbance of hexavalent chromium using 0.1 g of adsorbent in 200 ml of solution at different initial concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 1mg/l Cr(VI). The temperature of the solution during the process was 20 ° C. The pH was adjusted to 3 using a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid. After a 1 hour contact time under agitation, the solution was filtered to remove the adsorbent and the filtrate was used to measure the liquid concentrations.

Batch experiments were also conducted for the adsorption of organic matter (measures as total COD) using 1g of adsorbent in 100 ml of solution at different initial concentrations ranging from 2.66 to 12 g/l COD. The temperature of the solution during the process was 20 ° C. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 3 using a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid. After contacting for 2.5 hours under agitation, the solution was filtered to remove the adsorbent and a sample was taken from the filtrate. Determination of COD was performed according to ‘Standard Methods for the Examination of Water & Wastewater’– Method 5220D [22].

2.5.1 Adsorption isotherms

The biosorption isotherm is important in order to design a biosorption system. Each model is tested for the best fit in order to describe the equilibrium achieved. The two widely accepted and linearized equilibrium adsorption isotherm for single solute system are given by the Eq.1, Eq.2 and Eq.3.

Concentration q_e (mg/g) of the adsorbate on the surface of the adsorbent is calculated by Eq.1

$$q_e = \frac{(C_0 - C_e)}{W} V \quad (1)$$

where,

C_0, C_e = concentrations (mg/L) of the adsorbate initially and after equilibrium is achieved,

W = mass (g) of adsorbent used, V (L) the volume of the solution.

Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption models were used to fit the experimental data. The Langmuir model assumes monolayer sorption and its form is given by Eq.2:

$$\frac{1}{q_e} = \frac{1}{bQ} \frac{1}{C_e} + \frac{1}{Q} \quad (2)$$

where,

C_e = the concentration of Cr(VI) at equilibrium (mg/l),

q_e = the amount of adsorption of Cr(VI) at equilibrium (mg/g),

Q = the maximum adsorption capacity on the surface of adsorbent (mg/g), and

b = the equilibrium adsorption constant (l/mg).

A plot of $1/q_e$ versus $1/C_e$ gives a straight line with slope of $1/(b*Q)$, and intercept is $1/Q$.

The Freundlich isotherm is an empirical equation used for heterogeneous systems and its linear form is given by Eq.3:

$$\log q_e = \log K + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e \quad (3)$$

where, K and $1/n$ indicate the adsorption capacity and the adsorption intensity of the system, respectively.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 TGA of FORBI

Figure 2 TG (green) - dTG (grey) - dSC (red) curves of FORBI

Fig.2 presents (green curve) the mass loss progress in percentage of the initial mass of the sample during the heating program (TG). The grey curve corresponds to the mass loss rate (dTG%/min). The red curve is the heat flow during the heating program (above zero indicates that exothermic reactions take place and below zero endothermic). Examining these curves, it is clear that the highest percentile of mass loss and the highest mass loss rate occur in the temperature zone of 200–400°C. The dTG and TG curves stabilize at 770°C (85% mass loss) with minor losses after that point. So, a temperature of 800°C was decided to be optimal for carbonization /activation of the specific precursor, in order to achieve high carbon content in the final product. Based on this and on the literature, KOH was selected as activating agent, since its optimal activation temperature is 800°C [23].

3.2 Production yield

In Table 1 the yields for the 3 adsorbent samples prepared are given.

Table 1. Product Yield

	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
Yield (%)	14.6	13.1	15.9

The final product yield values taken are as expected from the examination of the TGA curves, due to excessive mass loss during the pyrolysis process.

3.3 BET specific surface area

Specific surface area (S_{BET}) values for the 3 samples and FORBI are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Specific surface area values for 3 samples and FORBI

	S_{BET} (m ² /g)
FORBI	2.5
Sample 1	56
Sample 2	47
Sample 3	35

Despite the fact that through the process the specific surface area of the raw material is multiplied, the values are quite lower than those of most activated carbons [19; 20; 24]. These results demonstrate a restricted development of porosity.

3.4 FTIR spectroscopy

The spectra for the 3 samples are shown in Figure 2. Comparing the 3 spectra with the KBr spectrum no distinctive peaks are observed, indicating excessive carbonization of the sample and absence of functional groups on the surface of the adsorbent.

Figure 1. FTIR Spectra of 3 samples (blue, red, green) vs KBr tablet spectrum (black)

3.5 Morphology of adsorbent by SEM images

Images observed in figures indicate a widely heterogeneous surface structure of the adsorbent. A desirable porous structure can be seen in Image 1 Image , which is achieved for some of the granules. Most of the granules though resemble those of Image 2, where high specific surface area structure is achieved but is rather superficial with no visible pore development. Some of the granules lack development of high specific surface structures or pores, as it can be seen in Image 3. Meanwhile others have formed pores of various diameters, Image 4.

Image 1. Porous structure

Image 2. High specific surface area, no pore development

Image 3. Lack of porous structure and specific surface area

Image 4. Various pores, no specific surface area

3.6 Adsorption of Cr(VI) and COD

3.1.1 Cr(VI) adsorption experiments

The removal capacity of the adsorbent in low concentrations is quite high as it can be seen in Table 3. The linear fit of Langmuir and Freundlich models (eq) are shown in Fig.3 and Fig.4. Adsorption parameters and R^2 are shown in Table 4. The Langmuir model has a better fit, suggesting that adsorption occurs as a monolayer sorption in this case.

Table 3. experimental data of Cr(VI) adsorption

C_0 (mg/L)	C_e (mg/L)	Reduction
0.1	0.0075	92.50%
0.2	0.0255	87.25%
0.3	0.055	81.67%
0.4	0.0537	86.58%
0.5	0.1675	66.50%
1	0.3691	63.09%

Figure 3. Langmuir linear fit for Cr(VI) adsorption

Figure 4. Freundlich linear fit for Cr(VI) adsorption

Table 4: Langmuir-Freundlich parameters for Cr(VI) adsorption

Langmuir	b	Q	R²
	35.91	0.870	0.955
Freundlich	n	K	R²
	2.179	1.910	0.919

3.1.2 COD adsorption experiments

The removal capacity of the adsorbent in high concentrations is moderate as it is indicated on Table 5. The linear fit of Langmuir and Freundlich models (eq) are shown in Figures 5 and 6. Adsorption parameters and R^2 are given in Table 6. The Freundlich model has a better fit in this case. The sample used was from the condensate of the dryer - shredder used in FORBI production. Depending on the drying conditions employed, this condensate can have a significant COD content as was the case for this particular sample. The use of Langmuir model proves to be rather unsuitable in this case. The percentile reduction may not be as high as in the case of Cr(VI), but the COD concentration was significantly reduced (from 12g/LCOD to 6.5g/L). Of course the exact composition of the organic material in a wastewater is expected to have a significant impact on the performance of an adsorbent in terms of reducing the organic content as determined by COD.

Table 5 experimental data for COD adsorption

C₀ (mg/l)	C_e (mg/l)	Reduction
2660	1658	37.67%
6000	3872	35.47%
8000	4698	41.28%
10000	5665	43.35%
12000	6509	45.76%

Figure 2. Langmuir linear fit for COD adsorption

Figure 6. Freundlich linear fit for COD adsorption

Table 6. Langmuir-Freundlich parameters for COD adsorption

Langmuir	b (l/mg)	Q(mg/g)	R ²
	-3.7E-05	-27393	0.984
Freundlich	n	K	R ²
	0.8163	0.0105	0.965

4. Conclusions

Although an activated carbon production process was followed in treating FORBI as starting biomass material, the final specific surface area of the samples did not approach that of most activated carbons. SEM images reveal a variation in developed structures. Some particles display the desired structure, whereas in others it is partially formed or not formed at all, which explains the restricted development of porosity measured by BET. Alongside the fact that FTIR displayed no functional groups, it can be concluded that the process was stressful for this precursor and that pore collapsing might have occurred in some granules. However, adsorption experiments had quite efficient results, especially in the case of Cr(VI) adsorption at low initial concentrations. The diversity of the precursor particles' microstructure seems to be the limiting factor in the effort to produce an adsorbent with high porosity.

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